

Assessing synergies between thermal energy and torrefaction severity index of wood spruce sawdust via machine learning algorithms

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ABSTRACT

Assessing the synergies between thermal energy and the torrefaction severity index by elucidating the effects of biomass torrefaction conditions on product characteristics is still a relevant research question. This study explores the optimization of torrefaction of spruce wood sawdust by analyzing the chemical and physical features of the resultant material. The study employs thermogravimetric analysis and Thermal Desorption-Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry (TD-GC/MS) to examine the changes in the components during torrefaction. The torrefaction process has a profound effect on the composition, causing conversion of up to 30 % of the initial mass to volatile organic compounds and incondensable gases when subjected to a temperature of 300 °C. The correlation matrix highlights the relationships between variables, including time, temperature, heating value, mass yield, energy yield, and ratios of C, H, and O. The matrix visually represents the interplay between these factors during the torrefaction process. Principal component analysis (PCA) and hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA) revealed that torrefaction severity index, cellulose, lignin, torrefaction time, and temperature correlate positively, while H/C, O/C, and hemicellulose content correlate negatively. The ANN model exhibited superior predictive accuracy ($R^2 = 0.99982$, RMSE = 0.00359), surpassing C&RT ($R^2 = 0.99483$, RMSE = 0.01943), KNN ($R^2 = 0.99467$, RMSE = 0.01974), and SVM ($R^2 = 0.99022$, RMSE = 0.02674), thus validating the efficacy of machine learning for precise torrefaction severity index (TSI) prediction. This finding enhances the efficiency of biomass processing and provides reliable tools for future research in the field, thereby informing and guiding future studies and industrial applications.

1. Introduction

Biomass torrefaction has emerged as a promising technology for improving the properties of lignocellulosic materials, contributing to the development of sustainable and efficient energy sources [1]. Torrefaction is a thermochemical process that enhances the characteristics of biomass by subjecting it to moderate temperatures (200–300 °C) in an environment with minimal or no oxygen [2]. This technique enhances biomass's energy density, grindability, and hydrophobicity, making it suitable for various applications, such as co-firing in coal power plants and as a feedstock for gasification or pyrolysis operations [3]. With its

abundant supply and potential as a biomass feedstock, spruce wood sawdust has garnered significant attention as a renewable energy source [4]. However, the research is still exploring the roles of thermal energy and torrefaction severity and their impact on product properties. This study explicitly investigates the optimization and application of spruce wood sawdust to understand better the correlation between the torrefaction process thermal energy and the severity index, related to the complex chemical and physical changes that occur during torrefaction.

In recent years, significant advancements have been made in comprehending the torrefaction process of spruce wood sawdust [5,6]. Researchers have examined how temperature and residence time impact

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torrefied spruce sawdust's chemical and physical characteristics [7,8]. However, the research is still struggling to explore key solutions to the following questions:

1. How do varying levels of torrefaction severity index correlate with the thermal energy output of wood spruce sawdust?
2. How can machine learning (ML) models be trained and accurately predict such relationship?
3. What ML methods are needed to examine the relationship between process parameters and the complete range of chemical and physical characteristics of torrefied spruce sawdust?
4. There is a lack of comprehension regarding the connections between torrefaction conditions and the changes in volatile organic compounds (VOCs) that occur throughout the process.
5. There is the need of a thorough examination of the interaction among several variables, such as time, temperature, higher heating value (HHV), mass yield, energy yield, and elemental composition.
6. No comprehensive information is available to understand the development and application of machine learning models to predict the correlation between process thermal energy and torrefaction severity index of wood spruce sawdust.

This study aims to fill these gaps by employing a comprehensive and diverse approach: (1) using thermogravimetric analysis to gain an in-depth understanding of the thermal decomposition characteristics of spruce wood sawdust during torrefaction, (2) using thermal desorption-gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (TD-GC/MS) to examine alterations in chemical constituents, providing a detailed understanding of the torrefaction process, (3) constructing a correlation matrix that would help to elucidate the interconnections among key factors, such as time, temperature, higher heating value (HHV), mass yield, energy yield, and elemental ratios (carbon, hydrogen, oxygen), and (4) utilising principal component analysis (PCA) to detect and measure the connections between variables, offering a detailed comprehension of the torrefaction process based on the thermal inputs. Hence the aim of the study is to:

1. Evaluate machine learning methods that can accurately forecast the relationship between thermal energy and torrefaction severity index of wood sawdust.
2. Evaluate the predictive precision of the constructed models under various torrefaction settings and feedstock properties.
3. Utilise machine learning insights to determine the most effective energy inputs for optimizing the torrefaction process of wood sawdust.
4. establish a thorough framework for incorporating machine learning models into the biomass torrefaction process, improving its scalability and flexibility to various biomass kinds.

2. Material and methods

The sawdust of spruce wood was acquired from a local sawmill processing wood from the Moravian-Silesian Beskydy mountains in the Czech Republic. To maintain uniformity, the sample was subjected to shredding, grinding, and sieving, resulting in particles smaller than 0.125 mm (which passed through a 120 Tyler mesh screen). The proximate analysis was conducted on a Mettler-Toledo TGA-DSC-2 instrument employing 70 mL alumina crucibles. Each sample, approximately 10 mg, was heated at a rate of 10 °C/min, reaching a temperature of 110 °C. This was done under a controlled flow of high-purity nitrogen gas, with a 50 mL/min streamflow and an additional protective gas flow of 20 mL/min. The samples were subjected to a temperature of 110 °C for 30 min to remove any remaining moisture, followed by a subsequent heating to 900 °C, which was maintained for 30 min. The reduction in mass during this stage is ascribed to the presence of volatile substances. The sample was then heated at 10 °C/min under an air atmosphere,

reaching a temperature of 950 °C. The resulting decrease in mass is attributed to fixed carbon [9]. The elemental analysis (FlashSmart CHNS/O Analyzer, ThermoScientific) was performed on the dry matter of the original biomass and torrefied biomass according to standard EN ISO 16948 [10], where oxygen concentration was calculated by difference:

$$\text{O}\% = 100 - \text{ash}\% - (\text{C}\% + \text{H}\% + \text{N}\% + \text{S}\%) \quad (1)$$

To quantify the lignin, hemicellulose and cellulose content in spruce wood sawdust, the methods outlined in ASTM D1106-21 [11], and the methodology reported earlier [12], were used.

Higher heating value (HHV) measures the energy content of biomass. Mass loss and HHV increase with increasing temperatures and holding times. HHV is calculated using the following equation [13]:

$$\text{HHV} \left(\frac{\text{MJ}}{\text{kg}} \right) = 0.341\text{C}\% + 1.322\text{H}\% - 12\text{O}\% - 12\text{N}\% - 0.153\text{ash}\% \quad (2)$$

Mass yield is the percentage of the residual mass in the solid phase after torrefaction, and was calculated using the following formula [14]:

$$\text{Mass yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{mass of torrefied biomass}}{\text{mass of original biomass}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Based on the mass yield and HHV, the energy yield is defined as follows [15]:

$$\text{Energy yield (\%)} = \text{Mass yield (\%)} \times \frac{\text{HHV of the torrefied biomass}}{\text{HHV of the original biomass}} \quad (4)$$

Energy density is defined as the ratio of energy yield to mass yield, as described by [16]:

$$\text{Energy density} = \frac{\text{Energy yield}}{\text{Mass yield}} \quad (5)$$

Torrefaction Severity Index (TSI) as a measurement tool for torrefaction was proposed by Chen et al. [17,18], defined as:

$$\text{TSI} = \frac{\Delta\text{WI}}{\Delta\text{WI}_{\text{ref}}} \quad (6)$$

where ΔWI and $\Delta\text{WI}_{\text{ref}}$ stand for the weight loss increments at a certain torrefaction and reference operations, respectively.

According to Silveira et al. [19], the TSI scale measures the severity of pre-treatment, with values ranging from 0.00 (no pre-treatment) to 1.00 (most severe) at 300 °C for 60 min.

2.1. Thermogravimetric analysis

Torrefaction was performed using a thermal analyser TGA/DSC 2. The dried spruce sawdust samples with an approximate mass of around 10 mg were placed in the crucible in each thermogravimetric experiment. The furnace was initially sparged with nitrogen to facilitate the removal of oxygen from the environment. A constant nitrogen supply was maintained throughout the experiment to maintain an oxygen-free environment. A constant heating rate of 30 °C/min was used to increase the sample temperature from room temperature (25 °C) to the isothermal final torrefaction temperature. The optimal temperature for torrefaction depends on the type of biomass being used. Three different temperatures (200, 250, and 300 °C) were tested in this case. The samples were held at each torrefaction temperature for various lengths of time: 10, 20, 30, 40, and 60 min. This is an important parameter affecting the severity of torrefaction, which in turn affects the properties of the resulting material.

2.2. Thermal desorption-gas chromatography/mass spectrometry

Thermal Desorption-Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry (TD-GC/MS) is a powerful analytical technique used to identify and quantify organic compounds to optimize biomass processing conditions, assess biomass quality, and identify potential contaminants or impurities. In this analysis, 200–500 µg biomass samples were subjected to a temperature increase from 50 to 300 °C at a heating rate of 60 °C/min. This TD step aims at releasing the organic compounds from the biomass matrix and transfer them into the GC/MS system for separation and analysis. The desorbed compounds were concentrated (+ 10 °C) in a cooled injection system (CIS, Gerstel). After concentration, the organic compounds were heated in CIS to a temperature of 300 °C, at a temperature heating rate of 10 °C/s, and a holding time of 10 min, and injected into GC/MS (Agilent, Santa Clara, USA) on a non-polar column HP5 ms (60 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 µm). The organic compounds were separated in the following program: 40 °C (2 min) to 310 °C (10 min), a temperature rise rate of 10 °C/min. Using standards, a mass spectrometer (Agilent, 5977 B) detected and quantified the organic compounds for *m/z* 50–650 am.

2.3. Statistical analysis

The correlation matrix offers a comprehensive overview of the associations between the various variables in the dataset. In the matrix each cell shows the correlation between two variables ranging between – 1 and 1, with – 1 indicating a perfect negative correlation, 0 indicating no correlation, and 1 indicating a perfect positive correlation. The *p*-value indicates significance, marked with *, **, or *** for correlations significant at the 5 %, 1 %, or 0.1 % level, respectively. The principal component analysis (PCA) and hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA) were used to investigate the influence of composition and process parameters on the quality of the torrefied biomass. PCA is a statistical technique used to reduce the dimensionality of a dataset while retaining most of the information [20]. The length and direction of the arrows, known as loadings, indicate variance between the original variables and the principal components (PC). A loading of 1 or – 1 suggests that the variable is equivalent to the principal component, while a loading close to 0 indicates that the principal component does not sufficiently explain the variable. Curves of the variables closely aligned on the PCA graph indicate positive correlations, whereas those with curves pointing in opposite directions indicate negative correlations. The eigenvalues (the sum of the squared loadings for each variable) highlight each principal component's relative importance in explaining the data variance. The PC with the largest eigenvalue explains the most variance in the data, while the PC with the smallest eigenvalue explains the least variance.

PCA has already been employed in the gasification process to classify biomass based on its properties, gasification conditions, and gas properties [21]. Furthermore, HCA dendrogram was constructed by employing standardized data and utilizing the Euclidean distance metric in conjunction with the group average clustering technique. HCA has also been applied to determine the optimal operating parameters for co-gasification of biowaste alongside bituminous coal and lignite [22].

2.4. Machine learning

Developing a robust TSI predictive model necessitates consideration of the complex, potentially non-linear relationships between input variables (temperature, residence time, biomass type) and the resulting TSI. Four machine learning algorithms, including artificial neural networks (ANNs), advanced classification and regression trees (CARTs), support vector machines (SVMs), and *k*-nearest neighbor (KNN) methods were chosen for this study. The selection of ML algorithms was based on the characteristics of the dataset and the capability of predicting the torrefaction process. Each of the four algorithms - ANN, C&RT, SVM, and KNN - possesses unique advantages making them appropriate for this

task. ANNs are highly effective at modeling complex, nonlinear input-output relationships.

Random division was used to split the dataset containing 203 data points into training (70 %), testing (15 %), and validation (15 %) subsets. The four machine learning algorithms were trained using the same dataset.

The suitability of ANN stems from its ability to learn and represent these complex relationships. Furthermore, ANNs can process high-dimensional datasets, effectively disregarding irrelevant features - a significant advantage when numerous input features are present. ANN utilize a multilayer perceptron (MLP) architecture consisting of an input, hidden, and output layer. The methodology comprises training the dataset, where the objective is to minimize the error between the output signals and the intended targets through careful tuning of the hidden layer neurons and their transfer function [23]. The neural network architecture employed activation functions (Identity, Logistic, Tanh, Exponential, and Sine), with hidden layer containing 3–11 neurons. Model training consisted of twenty iterations, selecting the model exhibiting the lowest validation root mean squared error (RMSE).

Employing advanced C&RT provides interpretable results, namely decision trees (DT) [24], facilitating an understanding of the correlations between inputs and predicted TSI values. The ability to interpret is crucial in decision-making, aiding in comprehending the factors impacting predictions. Partitioning the continuous dataset into subsets is a key aspect of using C&RT in regression tasks, where the mean values determine the predicted values. The incorporation of pruning in C&RT helps mitigate the challenge of overfitting. A maximum of 1000 levels or a minimum of 3 % observations per child node served as training termination criteria. Ten-fold cross-validation was performed to ensure model generalizability.

The suitability of SVMs is a consequence of their capacity to manage high-dimensional datasets and non-linear relationships. Furthermore, SVM offer robust predictive capabilities, even when noise or outliers are present, a significant advantage for real-world data analysis.

SVM algorithms are designed to find the hyperplane that provides the greatest possible separation of data points in the feature space [25]. Through learning, the model gains the capacity to identify the intricate relationships between input features and the output, thereby enabling it to make precise predictions. In this study, the SVM algorithm employed a radial basis function (RBF) kernel, a commonly chosen option for regression tasks [24]. SVM used an RBF kernel ($\gamma = 0.333$, degree = 3) with grid-searched parameters (Capacity: 1–10, ϵ : 0.1–0.5).

KNN is a simple, yet effective algorithm. As a non-parametric algorithm, this method does not require assumptions about the underlying data distribution, making it ideal for datasets with complex or unknown distributions. By examining the similarity between the features of new data and the training data, the KNN algorithm can predict its output [25]. Training for the KNN model involves a dataset that contained input features and corresponding output values. The algorithm utilized an Euclidean distance metric to quantify the similarity between the input features and the training data in this study. Through 10 fold cross-validation, the value of *k* (*k* = 1–5) which determines the number of nearest neighbours to consider, was optimized to attain the best possible performance [26].

The assessment of machine learning models' performance is typically determined using various metrics, which encompass R^2 (coefficient of determination), AME (average mean error), MSE (mean square errors), and RMSE (root mean squared error). A higher R^2 value and lower values of AME, MSE, and RMSE suggest superior model performance.

The following equations describe the formulation and definition of these metrics:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^p [TSI_i - TSI_i^m]^2}{\sum_{i=1}^p [TSI_i - \overline{TSI}]^2} \quad (7)$$

$$AME = \frac{1}{p} \left[\sum_{i=1}^p |T_{SI_i} - T_{SI_i}^m| \right] \quad (8)$$

$$MSE = \frac{1}{p} \left[\sum_{i=1}^p [T_{SI_i} - T_{SI_i}^m]^2 \right] \quad (9)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{p} \left[\sum_{i=1}^p [T_{SI_i} - T_{SI_i}^m]^2 \right]} \quad (10)$$

where p is the sample size used for model evaluation, $T_{SI_i}^m$ is the modeled TSI corresponding to measured TSI (T_{SI_i}), and $\overline{T_{SI_i}}$ is its average value.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Thermogravimetric and heating curves of biomass

Fig. 1(a) shows the weight loss and temperature curves of thermogravimetric (TG) experiments on spruce biomass samples torrefied at 200 °C, 250 °C, and 300 °C. The sample holding time was 10 min. Fig. 1(b) reports the weight loss increment of the three samples torrefied at 200 °C, 250 °C, and 300 °C with increasing holding time. As the temperature rises, as expected the weight loss increases, with the sample torrefied at 300 °C showing the most significant weight loss. It is evident in the figures that the torrefaction process causes a mass loss due to the release of the products formed by the partial decomposition of hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin. The hemicellulose decomposes at around 220–300 °C, followed by cellulose which partially decomposes, while only limited lignin decomposition occurs at 300 °C [27]. The torrefaction temperature has a more significant effect on mass loss than the reaction time, consistently with previous studies [28]. Up to 30 % of the biomass is converted to volatile organic compounds and incondensable gases [29]. The findings indicate that there was a comparable reduction in mass yield between the tests at temperatures of 200 °C and 300 °C (27 %), as well as between those at 250 °C and 300 °C (23 %). Niu et al. [30] stated that the optimal conditions (in terms of increased HHV and energy yield) for biomass torrefaction correspond to a 60–80 % mass yield of solids. Tumuluru et al. [31] defined similar conditions for the target of energy balance when the biomass loss reaches about 30 % of its initial dry mass. While a 30 % mass reduction is consistent with spruce sawdust, the thresholds exhibit variability depending on the feedstock e. g. 20–40 % for grasses [32]. Mass loss considerations are

application-dependent; pelletization processes benefit from lower mass loss, while gasification is enhanced by higher losses.

3.2. Mass and energy yield as a function of torrefaction temperature

Fig. 2 shows the mass yield (a) and energy yield (b) as a function of torrefaction temperature and time. Due to the decomposition of the biomass components, the mass and energy yields decrease with the increase in temperature and time. The results exhibit a minor difference when the torrefaction temperature was held at either 200 °C or 250 °C. However, a substantial decrease in yields was observed at a temperature of 300 °C and for longer torrefaction durations.

3.3. Torrefaction severity index and van Krevelen plot

Fig. 3 presents the Torrefaction Severity Index (TSI) plots as a function of the temperature and holding time. The TSI is a dimensionless parameter used to quantify the severity of torrefaction. It is calculated as the weight loss increment at a certain torrefaction operation divided by the weight loss increment at a reference operation. Exploring various torrefaction temperatures and durations, it was found that the operation conducted at 300 °C for 1 h achieves the highest degree of torrefaction. Therefore, this particular condition was established as the reference operation. Consequently, the TSI values are zero at the onset of torrefaction and reach unity under the conditions of 300 °C and 1 h. From the plots in Fig. 3 it is evident that the TSI increases with both temperature and holding time, with the first variable having the largest influence.

The van Krevelen plot shown in Fig. 4 helps to understand the effect of torrefaction on the biomass elemental composition. As the torrefaction temperature and time increase, both the H/C and O/C atomic ratios decrease, indicating a higher energy density of the torrefied biomass. This is because, after torrefaction, moisture and light volatile substances are removed from the original biomass, which has a high content of hydrogen and oxygen, leaving behind a relatively higher amount of carbon. This process leads to a mild to moderate biomass carbonization [33].

3.4. Statistical analysis of biomass torrefaction

The descriptive statistical analysis of the variables related to Spruce sawdust torrefaction is presented in Table 1.

Table 2 presents the Pearson correlation matrix between variables: time, temperature, HHV, mass yield, energy yield, TSI, C, H, O, and chemical constituents. The correlation coefficient between Time and

Fig. 1. Weight loss and temperature curves of TG experiments on Spruce sawdust torrefaction.

Fig. 2. Mass and energy yields as a function of torrefaction temperature and time.

Fig. 3. Torrefaction severity index (TSI) plots.

Fig. 4. van Krevelen diagram of Spruce sawdust torrefied samples.

Mass Yield is -0.375 , indicating a weak negative correlation, meaning that as Time increases, mass yield slightly decreases. Similarly, the correlation coefficient between HHV and TSI is 0.954 which is statistically significant, indicating a strong positive correlation between HHV and TSI. As HHV increases, TSI tends to grow as well. Torrefaction temperature and residence time are the most commonly influential factors affecting TSI [17]. The correlation matrix (Table 2) confirms the relationship between TSI and HHV, TSI and C, and TSI and temperature, where the TSI value increases with increasing temperature, HHV, and carbon concentration, and decreasing hydrogen concentration [34]. In the case of oxygen, as a parameter determining biocarbon quality, the TSI value increases with decreasing oxygen concentration. During torrefaction, O-rich volatile matter is released, causing an increase in HHV and biocarbon quality [35]. The correlation coefficient (Table 2) shows that the TSI value increases with decreasing energy yield, which was also confirmed by previous studies [18,19]. It was also demonstrated that the TSI value increases with increasing cellulose and lignin concentrations and decreasing hemicellulose concentrations, corresponding to the primary conversion of major biomass components during torrefaction [32].

Table 1
Descriptive statistics of the dataset of Spruce sawdust torrefaction.

	Temp. (°C)	Valid*	Mean	Std. Dev.	Minimum	Maximum
Time (min)	200	6	26.528	21.346	0	59.167
	250	6	26.667	21.602	0	60
	300	6	26.333	20.992	0	58
Mass Yield (%)	200	6	92.286	0.407	91.624	92.891
	250	6	88.13	2.877	83.993	92.213
	300	6	70.66	11.45	57.44	89.548
Energy Yield (%)	200	6	88.964	2.642	85.887	92.891
	250	6	87.274	2.484	85.279	92.213
	300	6	76.898	7.845	68.42	89.548
TSI (-)	200	6	0.181	0.01	0.167	0.197
	250	6	0.279	0.067	0.183	0.376
	300	6	0.689	0.269	0.246	1
HHV (MJ/kg)	200	6	17.902	0.528	17.26	18.57
	250	6	18.398	0.538	17.76	19.19
	300	6	20.367	1.193	18.57	22.12
C (%)	200	6	46.988	0.939	46.01	48.45
	250	6	48.307	1.324	46.94	50.63
	300	6	52.753	3.076	47.83	56.85
H (%)	200	6	5.707	0.101	5.58	5.87
	250	6	5.632	0.138	5.45	5.87
	300	6	5.575	0.164	5.42	5.87
O (%)	200	6	47.155	1.205	45.5	48.41
	250	6	45.903	1.4	43.49	47.42
	300	6	41.508	2.909	37.19	45.79
Cellulose (%)	200	6	396.111	7.301	382.2	402.36
	250	6	425.265	18.376	395.569	445.52
	300	6	438.89	21.714	395.569	451.02
Hemicellulose (%)	200	6	209.565	26.935	184.89	261.21
	250	6	195.037	33.391	172.73	261.21
	300	6	87.698	85.713	42.3	261.21
Lignin (%)	200	6	306.92	29.216	261.621	340.22
	250	6	328.082	35.352	261.621	363.95
	300	6	364.399	52.127	261.621	402.36
Lipid (%)	200	6	0.155	0.072	0.048	0.239
	250	6	0.2	0.058	0.098	0.248
	300	6	0.158	0.047	0.073	0.194
Terpenes (%)	200	6	0.045	0.031	0.02	0.097
	250	6	0.052	0.032	0.021	0.1
	300	6	0.055	0.033	0.023	0.099
Proteins (%)	200	6	0.022	0.012	0.011	0.043
	250	6	0.022	0.01	0.012	0.04
	300	6	0.018	0.004	0.012	0.022

* Number of data points.

3.5. Principal component analysis of biomass torrefaction

Fig. 5(a) depicts PCA biplot of spruce wood sawdust torrefaction, with variables such as O/C ratio, H/C ratio, concentration of cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin, residence time, torrefaction temperature, and TSI. The colored ellipses represent the 95 % confidence intervals for each torrefaction temperature. The variables are plotted as a function of two principal components (PC1 and PC2), which explain the majority of the variance in the data. The first principal component (PC1) accounts for 76.1 % of the variance, while the second principal component (PC2) explains another 13 %. The eigenvalues for PC1 and PC2 are 6.08961 and 1.03617, respectively. It is evident from Fig. 5(a) that the time has a pronounced effect through PC2 (0.82) and has a low correlation with the other variables, as indicated in Table 2 and Fig. 5(b). Temperature has a significant negative loading through PC2. H/C, O/C, and hemicellulose have negative loadings on PC1 and are clustered together in the PCA and HCA given in Fig. 5. On the other hand, cellulose, TSI, lignin, and temperature load positively on PC1. It is conceivable that H/C, O/C, and hemicellulose have a negative correlation with the concentration of cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin, residence time, torrefaction temperature, and TSI, which is consistent with the Pearson correlation given in Table 2 since their loading directions are opposite in Fig. 5(a). Thus, the torrefaction process can be optimized by adjusting the temperature and residence time to achieve a higher TSI, which indicates a more severe torrefaction process.

3.6. TSI prediction using machine learning

Fig. 6 (a–h) compares the regression and fitting plots for predicting the Torrefaction Severity Index (TSI) using four machine learning algorithms: Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Classification and Regression Trees (C&RT), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN). Fig. 6 demonstrates the predictive performance of each machine learning model for TSI on the actual data points. The regression plots indicate that the ANN model exhibit excellent performance, with minimal errors and a very high correlation between projected and actual TSI levels. The C&RT model similarly aligns with the data effectively but exhibits somewhat more deviations from the actual values than ANN. SVM performs worse than ANN, C&RT and KNN, with significant disparities between projected and actual TSI values. KNN also exhibits a lower prediction accuracy, demonstrating a diminished correlation between anticipated and real TSI. Each plot illustrates the efficacy of each model in aligning with the actual TSI values, with the ANN distinctly surpassing the others in predictive accuracy.

Table 3 compares the efficacy of the four machine learning algorithms in forecasting the Torrefaction Severity Index (TSI). The table presents the values of the four performance indicators for each machine learning model: AME (Average Mean Error), MSE (Mean Square Error), RMSE (Root Mean Square Error), and R² (coefficient of determination). These indicators facilitate the evaluation of the precision and efficacy of the models in forecasting TSI. The ANN model exhibits superior

Table 2
Pearson's correlation matrix of Spruce sawdust torrefaction.

Variable	Time	Temperature	MY	EY	TSI	HHV	C	H	O	Cellulose	Hemicellulose	Lignin	Lipid	Terpenes
Temperature	-0.004	—												
Mass Yield	-0.375	-0.785	***	—										
Energy Yield	-0.354	-0.702	***	0.962	***	—								
TSI	0.374	0.785	***	-1	***	0.962	***	—						
HHV	0.38	0.775	***	-0.954	***	0.841	***	0.954	***	—				
C	0.439	0.766	***	-0.975	***	0.883	***	0.975	***	0.991	***	—		
H	-0.586	-0.396	**	0.686	**	0.763	**	-0.629	**	0.685	**	-0.629	**	—
O	-0.42	-0.762	***	0.954	***	0.954	***	-0.995	***	0.997	***	-0.995	***	0.564
Cellulose	0.419	0.739	**	-0.777	***	-0.708	**	0.777	***	0.735	***	0.78	***	-0.706
Hemicellulose	-0.424	-0.671	**	0.919	***	-0.919	***	-0.868	***	-0.821	***	0.822	***	-0.826
Lignin	0.466	0.538	*	-0.806	***	-0.877	***	0.806	***	0.642	***	0.773	***	-0.892
Lipid	0.424	0.017	—	0.033	0.044	0.033	0.104	0.01	-0.117	0.22	0.105	-0.124	—	
Terpenes	0.291	0.139	-0.258	-0.309	0.258	0.144	0.179	-0.299	-0.122	0.453	-0.364	0.307	0.54	
Proteins	0.422	-0.165	0.067	0.031	-0.067	-0.124	-0.101	-0.046	0.141	0.225	-0.127	0.08	0.413	
														0.758

MY: mass yield; EY: energy yield; TSI: torrefaction severity index; HHV: higher heating value.

* $p < .05$.

** $p < .01$.

*** $p < .001$.

performance compared to the other models, evidenced by the lowest values of AME, MSE, and RMSE. The R^2 score is very high (0.99982), signifying that it forecasts TSI with remarkable precision and negligible error. The second-best model (C&RT) exhibits marginally more elevated error metrics compared to the ANN, although it remains a robust performer with a high R^2 of 0.99483. The third model (SVM) shows moderate performance, higher error metrics relative to ANN and C&RT, and a lower R^2 value (0.99022). Regarding the fourth model (KNN), although it exhibits comparable performance to C&RT in certain respects, it possesses more elevated error metrics and a little reduced R^2 (0.99467), rendering it the least accurate among the top three models.

3.7. TSI prediction using Taylor diagram

Fig. 7 illustrates a Taylor diagram that compares the efficacy of the four machine learning algorithms—ANN, C&RT, SVM, and KNN—in forecasting the Torrefaction Severity Index (TSI). A Taylor diagram is an effective instrument for evaluating the fidelity of models in replicating actual data by illustrating three principal statistics: correlation, root mean square error (RMSE), and the standard deviation of model predictions. ANN demonstrates very good performance with high correlation and low error. Its capacity to forecast the TSI surpasses that of alternative models, as evidenced by its closeness to the reference point. C&RT continues to demonstrate commendable performance, exhibiting a relatively high accuracy in forecasting TSI. Nevertheless, its inaccuracies are more evident than the ANN's, as shown by its increased deviation from the reference point. KNN exhibits mediocre performance, with more significant prediction errors than the leading two models. The position on the diagram suggests that its forecasts diverge significantly from the observed data, and the standard deviation may not align effectively with the observations. SVM has the lowest prediction accuracy, characterized by substantial errors and a standard deviation that may diverge from the observed data. Its diminished performance is signified by its greater distance from the optimal spot.

Given the pronounced non-linearity in the correlation between input and predicted TSI values, the ANN's adaptive learning mechanism proved more effective than that of C&RT. The findings suggest ANNs constitute a primary modeling choice for complex, nonlinear relationships, especially those involving large and diverse datasets. Nevertheless, employing C&RT remains a viable approach when prioritizing model interpretability and the input-output relationships exhibit relative simplicity.

4. Conclusions

This research delineates a definite correlation between thermal energy input and the Torrefaction Severity Index (TSI), illustrating how variations in torrefaction parameters (duration, temperature) influence spruce sawdust's chemical and physical characteristics. The robust association between Higher Heating Value (HHV) and TSI indicates that the torrefaction process can be refined to enhance energy density. The torrefaction process results in diminished mass yield while improving the energy density of biomass. Van Krevelen diagrams demonstrate a decline in H/C and O/C ratios as torrefaction severity increases, signifying enhanced biomass quality and energy potential. Multiple machine learning algorithms—ANN, C&RT, SVM, and KNN—were utilized to forecast the TSI based on process factors. The Artificial Neural Network (ANN) surpassed all other models, attaining the highest prediction accuracy, the lowest error rates (AME, MSE, RMSE), and a very high R^2 value of 0.99982. The research highlights the significance of machine learning in enhancing the torrefaction process by precise predictions of TSI across diverse torrefaction settings. The models developed in the study can function as dependable instruments for subsequent research and industrial applications, contributing to the improvement of sustainability and efficiency in biomass conversion technologies. The study establishes a framework for enhancing torrefied biomass quality and

Fig. 5. Biplot of (a) principal component analysis (PCA) and (b) hierarchical cluster analysis.

energy density by determining optimal process parameters, increasing its suitability for bioenergy applications. Subsequent studies could explore deep learning techniques (e.g., convolutional neural networks for image-based biomass analysis or transformer networks for multi-modal datasets), while artificial neural networks remain suitable for

current scalar inputs.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Scala Fabrizio: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project

Fig. 6. Comparison of regression and fitting plots for TSI prediction using (a&b) ANN, (c&d) advanced C&RT, (e&f) SVM and (g&h) KNN.

Table 3
Metrics for TSI prediction using different machine learning algorithms.

Net. name	AME	MSE	RMSE	R ²	Valid N *
ANN	0.00272	1.29E – 05	0.00359	0.99982	203
C&RT	0.00922	0.00038	0.01943	0.99483	203
SVM	0.02227	0.00072	0.02674	0.99022	203
KNN	0.01192	0.00039	0.01974	0.99467	203

* Number of data points.

Fig. 7. Taylor diagram for comparison of ANN, C&RT, SVM, and KNN models for predicting TSI. The Taylor diagram evaluates models via the following metrics: correlation (angular position), and standard deviation (radial distance from origin). Closer proximity to ‘Observed’ indicates better performance.

administration, Funding acquisition. **Ali Imtiaz:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Naqvi Salman Raza:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Raclavska Helena:** Methodology, Investigation. **Růžicková Jana:** Methodology, Investigation. **Šafář Michal:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Fabrizio Scala reports financial support was provided by Ministry of Education, Youth and Sport of the Czech Republic. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] A. Imtiaz Anando, M.M. Ehsan, M.R. Karim, A.A. Bhuiyan, M. Ahiduzzaman, A. Karim, Thermochemical pretreatments to improve the fuel properties of rice

- husk: a review, *Renew. Energy* 215 (2023) 118917, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2023.118917>.
- [2] K.-T. Lee, S. Gabriela, W.-H. Chen, H.C. Ong, S. Rajendran, K.-Q. Tran, Co-torrefaction and synergistic effect of spent coffee grounds and tea waste for sustainable waste remediation and renewable energy, *Renew. Energy* 233 (2024) 121181, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2024.121181>.
- [3] V. Sykrova, L. Jezerska, V. Sassmanova, S. Honus, P. Peikertova, J. Kielar, M. Zidek, Biomass pellets with organic binders – before and after torrefaction, *Renew. Energy* 221 (2024) 119771, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2023.119771>.
- [4] V.V. Dorokhov, G.S. Nyashina, D.S. Romanov, P.A. Strizhak, Combustion and mechanical properties of pellets from biomass and industrial waste, *Renew. Energy* 228 (2024) 120625, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2024.120625>.
- [5] C. Onyenwoke, L.G. Tabil, E. Mupondwa, D. Cree, P. Adapa, Effect of torrefaction on the physicochemical properties of white spruce sawdust for biofuel production, *Fuels* 4 (2023) 111–131, <https://doi.org/10.3390/fuels4010008>.
- [6] Y. Yang, X. Qu, G. Huang, S. Ren, L. Dong, T. Sun, P. Liu, Y. Li, T. Lei, J. Cai, Insight into lignocellulosic biomass torrefaction kinetics with case study of pinewood sawdust torrefaction, *Renew. Energy* 215 (2023) 118941, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2023.118941>.
- [7] K. Krochmalny, L. Niedzwiecki, E. Pelińska-Olko, M. Wnukowski, K. Czajka, M. Tkaczuk-Serafin, H. Pawlak-Kruczek, Determination of the marker for automation of torrefaction and slow pyrolysis processes – a case study of spherical wood particles, *Renew. Energy* 161 (2020) 350–360, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2020.07.100>.
- [8] S. Riaz, I. Oluwoye, Y.M. Al-Abdeli, Oxidative torrefaction of densified woody biomass: performance, combustion kinetics and thermodynamics, *Renew. Energy* 199 (2022) 908–918, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.09.023>.
- [9] J. Xue, T. Chellappa, S. Ceylan, J.L. Goldfarb, Enhancing biomass + coal Co-firing scenarios via biomass torrefaction and carbonization: case study of avocado pit biomass and Illinois No. 6 coal, *Renew. Energy* 122 (2018) 152–162, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2018.01.066>.
- [10] A. Iglesias Canabal, J. Proupin Castiñeiras, J.A. Rodríguez Añón, C. Emil Fraga, R. Rodríguez Soalleiro, Elemental composition of raw and torrefied pellets made from pine and pine-eucalyptus blends, *Biomass Bioenergy* 177 (2023) 106951, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2023.106951>.
- [11] Standard Test Method for Acid-Insoluble Lignin in Wood, 2021. (<https://doi.org/10.1520/D1106-21>).
- [12] Chlorite holocellulose, its fractionation and bearing on summative wood analysis and on studies on the hemicelluloses, 1946.
- [13] R. Amen, J. Hameed, G. Albashar, H.W. Kamran, M.U. Hassan Shah, M.K. U. Zaman, A. Mukhtar, S. Saqib, S.I. Ch, M. Ibrahim, S. Ullah, A.G. Al-Sehemi, S. R. Ahmad, J.J. Klemes, A. Bokhari, S. Asif, Modelling the higher heating value of municipal solid waste for assessment of waste-to-energy potential: a sustainable case study, *J. Clean. Prod.* 287 (2021) 125575, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125575>.
- [14] E.A. Silveira, B.-J. Lin, B. Colin, M. Chaouch, A. Pétrissans, P. Rousset, W.-H. Chen, M. Pétrissans, Heat treatment kinetics using three-stage approach for sustainable wood material production, *Ind. Crops Prod.* 124 (2018) 563–571, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2018.07.045>.
- [15] K.-M. Lu, W.-J. Lee, W.-H. Chen, S.-H. Liu, T.-C. Lin, Torrefaction and low temperature carbonization of oil palm fiber and eucalyptus in nitrogen and air atmospheres, *Bioresour. Technol.* 123 (2012) 98–105, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2012.07.096>.
- [16] N. Prasongthum, N. Duangwongsa, P. Khowattana, A. Suemanotham, P. Wongharn, Y. Thanmongkhon, P. Reubroycharoen, L. Attanatho, Influence of torrefaction on yields and characteristics of densified solid biofuel, *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* 2175 (2022) 012027, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2175/1/012027>.
- [17] W.-H. Chen, R. Aniza, A.A. Arpia, H.-J. Lo, A.T. Hoang, V. Goodarzi, J. Gao, A comparative analysis of biomass torrefaction severity index prediction from machine learning, *Appl. Energy* 324 (2022) 119689, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.119689>.
- [18] W.-H. Chen, C.-L. Cheng, P.-L. Show, H.C. Ong, Torrefaction performance prediction approached by torrefaction severity factor, *Fuel* 251 (2019) 126–135, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2019.04.047>.
- [19] E.A. Silveira, S. Luz, K. Candelier, L.A. Macedo, P. Rousset, An assessment of biomass torrefaction severity indexes, *Fuel* 288 (2021) 119631, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2020.119631>.
- [20] S. Wold, K. Esbensen, P. Geladi, Principal component analysis, *Chemom. Intell. Lab. Syst.* 2 (1987) 37–52, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-7439\(87\)80084-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-7439(87)80084-9).
- [21] M. Dellavedova, M. Derudi, R. Biesuz, A. Lunghi, R. Rota, On the gasification of biomass: data analysis and regressions, *Process Saf. Environ. Prot.* 90 (2012) 246–254, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2011.08.001>.
- [22] N. Howaniec, A. Smoliński, Biowaste utilization in the process of co-gasification with bituminous coal and lignite, *Energy* 118 (2017) 18–23, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2016.12.021>.
- [23] I. Argatov, Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) as a Novel Modeling Technique in Tribology, 2019. (<https://depositonce.tu-berlin.de/handle/11303/9574>) (Accessed 26 July 2024).
- [24] C.-C. Chang, C.-J. Lin, LIBSVM: a library for support vector machines, *ACM Trans. Intell. Syst. Technol.* 2 (2011), <https://doi.org/10.1145/1961189.1961199> (27:1–27:27).
- [25] H. Drucker, C.J.C. Burges, L. Kaufman, A. Smola, V. Vapnik, Support vector regression machines, in: *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, MIT Press, 1996. (https://papers.nips.cc/paper_files/paper/1996/hash/d38901788c533e8286cb6400b40b386d-Abstract.html) (Accessed 26 July 2024).

- [26] J.M. Keller, M.R. Gray, J.A. Givens, A fuzzy K-nearest neighbor algorithm, *IEEE Trans. Syst. Man Cybern. SMC-15* (1985) 580–585, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMC.1985.6313426>.
- [27] H. Yang, R. Yan, H. Chen, D.H. Lee, C. Zheng, Characteristics of hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin pyrolysis, *Fuel* 86 (2007) 1781–1788, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2006.12.013>.
- [28] R.N.U.A. Rahman, R.A. Rasid, M. Ismail, Effect of temperature and residence time on the characteristics of torrefied food, *IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.* 702 (2019) 012002, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/702/1/012002>.
- [29] S. Barskov, M. Zappi, P. Buchireddy, S. Dufreche, J. Guillory, D. Gang, R. Hernandez, R. Bajpai, J. Baudier, R. Cooper, R. Sharp, Torrefaction of biomass: a review of production methods for biocoal from cultured and waste lignocellulosic feedstocks, *Renew. Energy* 142 (2019) 624–642, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2019.04.068>.
- [30] Y. Niu, Y. Lv, Y. Lei, S. Liu, Y. Liang, D. Wang, S. Hui, Biomass torrefaction: properties, applications, challenges, and economy, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 115 (2019) 109395, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.109395>.
- [31] J.S. Tumuluru, B. Ghiasi, N.R. Soelberg, S. Sokhansanj, Biomass torrefaction process, product properties, reactor types, and moving bed reactor design concepts, *Front. Energy Res.* 9 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2021.728140>.
- [32] T.R. Sarker, S. Nanda, A.K. Dalai, V. Meda, A review of torrefaction technology for upgrading lignocellulosic biomass to solid biofuels, *Bioenerg. Res.* 14 (2021) 645–669, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12155-020-10236-2>.
- [33] W.-H. Chen, M.-Y. Huang, J.-S. Chang, C.-Y. Chen, Torrefaction operation and optimization of microalga residue for energy densification and utilization, *Appl. Energy* 154 (2015) 622–630, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.05.068>.
- [34] A. Becker, V. Scherer, A comparison of the torrefaction behavior of wood, miscanthus and palm kernel shells: measurements on single particles with geometries of technical relevance, *Fuel* 224 (2018) 507–520, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2018.01.095>.
- [35] A. Zhao, S. Liu, J. Yao, F. Huang, Z. He, J. Liu, Characteristics of bio-oil and biochar from cotton stalk pyrolysis: effects of torrefaction temperature and duration in an ammonia environment, *Bioresour. Technol.* 343 (2022) 126145, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2021.126145>.